

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF CUTANEOUS LEISHMANIASIS CASES IN RAMADI

Othman M. Mohammed

Department of Medical Laboratories Techniques, College of Health and Medical Technology, University of Al Maarif, Al Anbar, 31001, Iraq

Abstract: Background: Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a significant public health issue in Iraq and worldwide, caused by two types of parasites, *L. major* and *L. tropica*, which lead to different ulcers.

Materials: The study was conducted at Ramadi Teaching Hospital and dermatology clinics from October 1, 2022, to March 1, 2023. It included 120 suspected cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis. Demographic data was collected using a form.

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to analyze the demographic distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis cases in terms of sex, age, residential area, and the type and number of lesions, as well as to determine the seasonal variation of the disease.

Results: Out of 120 patients, 66 were males (55%) and 54 were females (45%), with no significant difference in infection rates between sexes. The ages of the patients ranged from 1 year to 60 years, with an average age of 31 years. The highest infection rates were observed in the age groups 1-10 and 21-30 years, while the lowest rates were in the age groups 41-50 and 51-60 years. Infection rates were significantly higher in rural areas (59.2%) compared to urban areas (40.8%). The highest infection rate according to months was in January (35.8%), and the lowest was in October (5.9%). Wet lesions were more common (51.7%) than dry ulcers (48.3%). Patients with 2-3 ulcers had the highest percentage (41.7%), followed by those with a single ulcer (37.5%), and the lowest percentage was for those with more than 5 ulcers (9.2%).

Conclusions: The study found that cutaneous leishmaniasis affects both sexes with a slight predominance in males. The disease is more prevalent in younger age groups and in rural areas. There is a significant seasonal variation in the occurrence of the disease, with the highest rates in January and the lowest in October. Wet lesions are more common than dry ulcers, and the majority of patients have 2-3 ulcers. These findings can help in the development of targeted public health strategies for the prevention and control of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Keywords: Cutaneous Leishmaniasis; Epidemiology; Demographic Distribution; Infection Rates; Rural-Urban Disparity.

1. Introduction

Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a tropical disease caused by single-celled parasites of the genus *Leishmania*, a disease transmitted by sand flies of the genus *Phlebotomus* in the Mediterranean and the Middle East and the genus *Lutzomyia* in South and Central America. The disease spreads in 98 countries in the world, There are More than 350 million people are at risk and nearly 2 million

people worldwide are infected with leishmaniasis each year, Leishmaniasis accounts for 5 to 10% of the illnesses of tourists returning from the tropics (Gregorio et al., 2019, Bastola et al., 2020).

In Iraq, there are two types of cutaneous leishmaniasis, *L. tropica* or anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ACL), and *L. major* (zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ZCL), In Iraq, there are two types of sand flies namely *P. papatasi*, *P. sergenti*, (Al-Warid et al., 2017, Slama et al., 2014). The innate immune response of the host infected with cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) works through Natural killer cells (NK) cells, macrophages, dendritic cells (DC), neutrophils, cytokines, chemokines, as well as complement proteins. Macrophages, dendritic cells, and neutrophils are the primary immune cells of the host that They are recruited to the infection site early after infection and can become infected by parasites (Matheoud et al., 2013).

The life cycle of the parasite begins when a female sand fly becomes infected during a blood meal, whether it is a human or animal host (Pimenta et al., 2018). The parasite develops within 4-25 days inside the vector and transforms into a promastigote form where it reproduces by binary fission in the midgut and moves towards the pharynx (Kreier, 2013). The infection will then spread within a few days after ingestion when there is acute pharyngitis. Therefore, the promastigote will be secreted by the insect bite of the host while taking blood (Paul, 2024). When the sand fly feeds on blood, macrophages immediately rush in and engulf the invading body through phagocytosis (Avila and Harris, 2013). Thus, these organelles enter the host, the organisms lose their flagella, amastigotes are formed and continue to multiply until the cells of the infected host are filled with organisms, then they burst, releasing free mastigotes that invade new cells, thus continuing the vicious cycle of Leishmania infection (Walker et al., 2014, Krueger and Engstler, 2015). Due to the complexity of the life cycle, the unavailability of a human vaccine, and the presence of multiple biological vectors and reservoir hosts, disease control remains elusive (Choy et al., 2022). Therefore, chemotherapy remains the main strategy for disease control. Various factors influence the non-response to treatment of leishmaniasis, such as social and geographical causes, clinical characteristics, type of diseases, Leishmania species, and host immune response (Bamorovat et al., 2021).

Although most prevention and control strategies have focused on reducing human-vector interactions using insecticide-treated materials and insect repellents, they only provide 50-65% protection against ZCL and their long-term sustainability is debatable, as the main reservoir host for ZCL in The Middle East and Central Asia are rodents of the species *Rhombomys opimus* (Rajabi et al., 2018). The incidence of CL in Iraq in the period (1989-2011) was lower than in Syria and Saudi Arabia but higher than in Jordan. Risk factors for this disease include malnutrition, poor hygiene, age, sex, geographical distribution and seasonality (Al-Obaidi et al., 2016). Prevention of the disease by vaccine is still ongoing, as a combination of killed vaccine and Bacillus Calmette-Guérin vaccine has been tested in Iran, Sudan and Ecuador (Volpedo et al., 2021, Modabber et al., 2016). Other methods of prevention may be successful, such as avoiding sand flies and using insecticide sprays (Gálvez et al., 2018). The purpose of the study was to investigate the epidemiological characteristics of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Iraq, specifically focusing on the distribution of the disease among different demographic groups, geographical locations, and time periods. Additionally, the study aimed to compare the prevalence of the two types of lesions caused by *L. major* and *L. tropica*, and to analyze the number of ulcers per patient. The research sought to identify patterns and significant differences in infection rates across various variables, such as age, sex, urban versus rural residence, and seasonal variations, to better understand the disease's impact and to inform public health strategies for prevention and control.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Design and Study Population

The study involved a cohort of 120 patients diagnosed with cutaneous leishmaniasis, with ages spanning from 1 to 60 years. The research was carried out at the Department of Dermatology and Venereology at Ramadi Teaching Hospital, where numerous cases of the condition were reported by specialized physicians. At the Dermatology Unit, comprehensive data on each patient was collected, encompassing their gender, age, the site of infection on their body, the date of infection, the count of ulcers, and the classification of the ulcer.

2.2 Laboratory diagnosis

According to (Ekşi et al., 2017), with some modifications, the lesion was cleaned thoroughly using 70% alcohol, and when patients were injected into the site of infection with a pentostam injection into the dermis using a sterile syringe (1mL, 30G * 1/2), We take by means of capillary tubes containing an anticoagulant the blood liquid that is secreted after injections of patients, where a drop of blood is placed on glass slides for the purpose of staining samples with *Leishman* stain or ready-made Giemsa stain produced by (Jourilabs, Turkey)to detect the amastigotes stage of the parasite.

3.2 statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 22. With regard to variables with a descriptive formula, they were described in the form of number and percentage, and the comparison was made using the Chi-square test.

4. Result

1.4. Distribution of Cutaneous leishmaniasis suspected patients according to gender.

The current study showed that with regard to the distribution of infected people by gender, there were no statistical differences between males and females infected with *Leishmania* parasite at the level of probability ($p > 0.05$), as shown in Table (1).

Table (1): Distribution of patients by gender

gender	NO of cases CL	Percent of cases CL(%)	P -value
male	66	55	p>0.05 NS NS: No significant
female	54	45	
Total	120	100%	

2.4. Distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis patients according to age group

The current study showed that there are significant differences between the percentages of the age groups, where the age groups 1-10, 21-30 years recorded the highest infection rate (35.8% and 25.0%), respectively, compared to the 31-40, 41-50, 11-20 , 51-60 years, which recorded the lowest percentage (10.8%, 8.3%, 2.5%, and 17.5%), respectively, at the probability level ($p < 0.001$), as shown in Table (2).

Table (2): Distribution according to age of patients

Age grope	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	P-value
1-10	43	35.8	p<0.001*** Significant
11-20	21	17.5	
21-30	30	25.0	
31-40	13	10.8	
41-50	10	8.3	
51-60	3	2.5	
Total	120	100%	

3.4. Distribution of suspected cutaneous leishmaniasis patients according to residence

The current study showed that there are significant differences at the probability level ($p < 0.05$) in terms of residential areas. The results also showed that the percentage of people who live in rural areas recorded the highest percentage (59.2%) compared to urban areas (40.8%), as shown in the table (3).

Table (3): Distribution according to residential areas of infected patients

Type of Residence	NO of cases CL	Percent(%)	P-value
Urban region	49	40.8	p<0.05* Significant
Rural region	71	59.2	
Total	120	100%	

4.4. Distribution of suspected cutaneous leishmaniasis suspected patient according to months

The current study showed that there are significant differences between the percentages in terms of months of the year. January recorded the highest infection rate (35.3%) compared to October, which recorded the lowest infection rate (5.9%) at the probability level ($p < 0.001$) as shown In the table (4)

Table (4): Distribution of patients according to months of sample collection.

Months	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	p-value
October	7	5.9	p<0.001*** Significant
November	18	15.1	
December	35	28.6	
January	42	35.3	
February	18	15.1	
Total	120	100%	

5.4. Distribution of Cutaneous leishmaniasis suspected patients according to the type of lesion.

The results of the current study show that there are significant differences between the percentages in terms of type of ulceration, wet ulceration recorded 51.7% higher than dry ulceration 48.3% at the level of probability $p < 0.001$ as shown in Table (5) and picture (1).

Table (5): Distribution of patients according to lesion type

Type of Lesion	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	P-value
Dry type	58	48.3	p<0.001*** Significant
Wet type	62	51.7	
Total	120	100%	

Picture (1) of patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis, A - Dry lesion type B - Wet lesion type

6.4. Distribution of patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis according to the location and number of lesion.

The current study showed that there were significant differences at the level of probability ($p < 0.001$), the number of ulcers 1 and 2-3 recorded the highest percentage (37.5% and 41.7%), respectively, compared to the number greater than 5, which recorded the lowest percentage (9.2%), as it showed The current study showed that there were significant differences in the distribution of the injured according to the site of the ulcer, where the face and hands recorded the highest percentage of ulcers (27.5% and 43.3%), respectively, compared to the abdomen and the feet, which recorded the lowest percentage (21.7, 7.5%), respectively, as shown in Table (6) and the picture (2)

Table (6): Distribution of infected patients according to the location and number of ulcers.

Location lesion	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	P-value
Face	33	27.5	p<0.001*** Significant
feets	26	21.7	
Hands	52	43.3	
abdomen	9	7.5	
Total	120	100%	
Number of lesion	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	p<0.001*** Significant
1	45	37.5	
2-3	50	41.7	
3-4	14	11.7	
>5	11	9.2	
Total	120	100%	

Picture (2): Some patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis in Ramadi city, (A): The number of ulcers is one,(B): The number of ulcers is 2-3,(c): The number of ulcers is from 4-5,(D): The location of the lesion is on the face,(E): The lesion site is in the left feet,(F): The location of the lesion is in the left hand.

7.4. Distribution of patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis according to the results of microscopic examination.

The results of the current study showed that there were significant differences at the level of probability ($p < 0.05$) between the positive and negative results of the microscopic examination of infected patients, as shown in Table (7) and Figure (3).

Table (7): Results of direct smear microscopy through a compound microscope

microscopic examination	NO of cases CL	Percent (%)	P-value
Positive	41	67.2	P<0.05*
Negative	20	32.8	
Total	61	100%	

Figure (3) Detection of amastigote form of cutaneous leishmaniasis parasite by direct blood smear method by direct compound microscopy (Giemsa stain, X40).

5. Discussion

In terms of demographic epidemiological data, initially, although there were no statistically significant differences between the genders, the present study found that 66 (55%) of those infected were males and 54 (45%) were females. These proportions are in line with the research conducted by (Al-Ani, 2018) in the city of Ramadi, and the study by (Al-Hassani, 2016) in Al-Qadisiyah Governorate. Furthermore, (El-Safi and Peters, 1991) asserted that males are more frequently affected than females, attributing this to males' greater exposure to the external environment and their lesser coverage of the body compared to women, due to social customs. Also, through these results, the disease appears in all age groups, but in varying proportions, and this was confirmed by (Durrani et al., 2011, Organization, 2000), where infections appear in age groups less than ten years due to the lack of development of the person's immune system and the inability to defend against the stings of the vector insect, The results of our research agreed with many researchers in Iraq, including a study (Rahi, 2013) in Wasit, a study (OLEIWI et al., 2021) in Dhi Qar, and a study (Al-Difaie and Ghyda, 2014) in Al-Qadisiyah Governorate, where they recorded a higher infection rate for rural areas than urban areas, The reason for the occurrence of infections in rural areas more than in urban areas is due to a number of reasons, including the geographical location close to the mountains and in which water streams flow throughout the year, and the abundance of fresh water that provides the vector insect with a suitable environment to complete its life cycle and increase agriculture (Asmaa et al., 2017). The population in agriculture near their homes where sand flies are present, and because most people residing in endemic areas are not aware of the disease.

The highest rate was recorded in January at 35.3%, followed by December at 28.6%, then February and November at 15.1%, and the lowest in October at 5.9%, This is consistent with the study of (Abul-Hab and al-Baghdadi, 1972)) where he showed that the peak of the spread of the fly and the life cycle of the parasite is from 4 to 6 months, where the spread of the fly occurs in May and September and the infection appears in January and February, Through our results, ulcers or a wet lesion appeared higher than dry ulcers, which explains this. It is known that *Leishmania major* abounds in rural areas from urban areas, unlike *Leishmania tropic*, so the results were consistent with what was recorded in this study.

Secondly, with regard to topographical data, we had the highest infection rate in the hands, followed by the face, and the lowest in the abdomen. This explains what was shown by (Rassam et al., 1985) the most exposed parts of the body to sand fly bites during lactation more than the other, or because the urban dry form tends to appear especially on the face, while the buccal (wet) type often appears on the arms and feet almost equally, as between (Tavares et al., 2003) the different clinical characteristics of cutaneous

leishmaniasis depending on the type of leishmaniasis infection and the immune response of the host, as well as our study recorded the wet type more than the dry type, so the highest percentage appeared in patients with two hands.

Third, the microscopic diagnosis was of importance through the appearance of the amastigote phase of the parasite in patients. The results of the study showed (67.2%) of the positive samples tested by the direct smear method (blood film), which is consistent with the study (Dawood, 2016), which indicated that the positive smears are 63.4. % and the negative is 36.6%. The results also coincided with the findings of (Luz et al., 2009), where 66% had a positive swab and 34% had a negative test, as it agreed with the study (Izadi et al., 2016)) where they showed 64.2% positive smear by microscopic examination, As pointed out by (Rahi, 2015) the diagnosis of CL classically relies on microscopic examination and culture in vitro. This classicism requires the presence of a relatively large number of viable or morphologically healthy parasites. This may pose a problem especially in the chronic phase of CL where parasite levels appear in skin lesions are very low, so in the current study we had 32.8% of negative smears tested by microscopy.

Conclusions

The study found that males were more commonly infected with cutaneous leishmaniasis, which is consistent with previous research. The disease affected all age groups, with children under ten being particularly susceptible due to their underdeveloped immune systems. Rural areas had higher infection rates than urban areas, likely due to their proximity to sand fly habitats and agricultural practices. The peak infection months were January and December, correlating with the life cycle of the parasite and the activity of the vector insect. Wet lesions were more prevalent than dry ones, which is expected given the abundance of *Leishmania major* in rural areas. The most common sites of infection were the hands and face, which are the most exposed body parts to sand fly bites. Microscopic diagnosis revealed that 67.2% of samples tested positive for the parasite, which is in line with other studies. However, 32.8% of smears were negative, highlighting the challenges of diagnosing CL in its chronic phase when parasite levels are low.

References

1. ABUL-HAB, J. & AL-BAGHDADI, R. 1972. Seasonal occurrence of man-biting *Phlebotomus* (Diptera: Psychodidae) in the Baghdad area, Iraq. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol*, 66, 165-6.
2. AL-ANI, S. F. 2018. Detection of cutaneous Leishmaniasis based on ITS1 gene by PCR-RFLP technique. *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences, E. Medical Entomology & Parasitology*, 10, 1-13.
3. AL-DIFAIE, R. & GHYDA, D. 2014. Study for the detection of cutaneous leishmaniasis parasite with identifying the type of parasite and diagnose the most important histopathological changes accompanying the parasite. *Basrah Journal of Veterinary Research*, 11
4. AL-HASSANI, M. K. 2016. دراسة وبائية وتشخيصية مظهرية وجزيئية لداء اللشمانيا الجلدية ونواقلها الحشرية (ذبابة الرمل) في قضاء الحمزة الشرقي, محافظة القادسية *Phlebotominae Sand fly Psychodidae Phlebotomus papatasi Sergentomyia sintoni Nested PCR cytochrome b (Cytb) gene DNA*.
5. AL-OBAIDI, M., YASEEN, M. & AL-SAQUR, I. 2016. Survey Study on the Prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 57, 2181-2187.
6. AL-WARID, H. S., AL-SAQUR, I. M., AL-TUWAIJARI, S. B. & ZADAWI, K. A. A. 2017. The distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Iraq: demographic and climate aspects. *Asian Biomedicine*, 11, 255-260.

7. ASMAA, Q., AL-SHAMERII, S., AL-TAG, M., AL-SHAMERII, A., LI, Y. & OSMAN, B. H. 2017. Parasitological and biochemical studies on cutaneous leishmaniasis in Shara'b District, Taiz, Yemen. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob*, 16, 47.
8. AVILA, J.-L. & HARRIS, J. R. 2013. *Intracellular parasites*, Springer Science & Business Media.
9. BAMOROVAT, M., SHARIFI, I., DABIRI, S., SHAMSI MEYMANDI, S., KARAMOOZIAN, A., AMIRI, R., HESHMATKHAH, A., BORHANI ZARANDI, M., AFLATOONIAN, M. R., SHARIFI, F., KHEIRANDISH, R. & HASSANZADEH, S. 2021. Major risk factors and histopathological profile of treatment failure, relapse and chronic patients with anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis: A prospective case-control study on treatment outcome and their medical importance. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 15, e0009089.
10. BASTOLA, A., SHRESTHA, M., LAMSAL, M., SHRESTHA, S., PRAJAPATI, S., ADHIKARI, A., GUPTA, B. P., HIDE, M., DEVKOTA, L. & CHALISE, B. S. 2020. A case of high altitude cutaneous leishmaniasis in a non-endemic region in Nepal. *Parasitology international*, 74, 101991.
11. CHOY, R. K., BOURGEOIS, A. L., OCKENHOUSE, C. F., WALKER, R. I., SHEETS, R. L. & FLORES, J. J. C. M. R. 2022. Controlled human infection models to accelerate vaccine development. 35, e00008-21.
12. DAWOOD, K. A. 2016. Pathological Study of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Al-Diwaniya province. *Al-Qadisiyah Medical Journal*, 12, 6-15.
13. DURRANI, A. Z., DURRANI, H. Z., KAMAL, N. & MEHMOOD, N. 2011. Prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in humans and dogs in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 43.
14. EKŞİ, F., ÖZGÖZTAŞI, O., KARSLIĞIL, T. & SAĞLAM, M. 2017. Genotyping Leishmania promastigotes isolated from patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis in south-eastern Turkey. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 45, 114-122.
15. EL-SAFI, S. H. & PETERS, W. 1991. Studies on the leishmaniasis in the Sudan. 1. Epidemic of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Khartoum. *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 85, 44-47.
16. GÁLVEZ, R., MONTOYA, A., FONTAL, F., DE MURGUÍA, L. M. & MIRÓ, G. J. R. I. V. S. 2018. Controlling phlebotomine sand flies to prevent canine Leishmania infantum infection: A case of knowing your enemy. 121, 94-103.
17. GREGORIO, A., VASCONCELLOS, M., ENOKIHARA, M., GUERRA, J., NONOGAKI, S. & TOMIMORI, J. 2019. Cutaneous schistosomiasis and leishmaniasis coinfection: a case report. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*, 33, 1781-1783.
18. IZADI, S., MIRHENDI, H., JALALIZAND, N., KHODADADI, H., MOHEBALI, M., NEKOEIAN, S., JAMSHIDI, A. & GHATEE, M. A. 2016. Molecular Epidemiological Survey of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Two Highly Endemic Metropolises of Iran, Application of FTA Cards for DNA Extraction From Giemsa-Stained Slides. *Jundishapur J Microbiol*, 9, e32885.
19. KREIER, J. P. 2013. *Parasitic Protozoa: Volume 10*, Academic Press.
20. KRUEGER, T. & ENGSTLER, M. Flagellar motility in eukaryotic human parasites. *Seminars in cell & developmental biology*, 2015. Elsevier, 113-127.
21. LUZ, Z. M., SILVA, A. R., SILVA FDE, O., CALIGIORNE, R. B., OLIVEIRA, E. & RABELLO, A. 2009. Lesion aspirate culture for the diagnosis and isolation of Leishmania spp. from patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz*, 104, 62-6.

22. MATHEOUD, D., MORADIN, N., BELLEMARE-PELLETIER, A., SHIO, M. T., HONG, W. J., OLIVIER, M., GAGNON, E., DESJARDINS, M. & DESCOTEAUX, A. 2013. Leishmania evades host immunity by inhibiting antigen cross-presentation through direct cleavage of the SNARE VAMP8. *Cell host & microbe*, 14, 15-25.
23. MODABBER, F., COLER, R. & REED, S. G. 2016. Vaccines against Leishmania. *New generation vaccines*. CRC Press.
24. OLEIWI, A. H., AL-KHUZAIE, A. A. M. & MOHAMMED, Z. J. 2021. Epidemiological study of cutaneous leishmaniasis patients in Thi-Qar Province, Iraq. *Iranian Journal of Ichthyology*, 8, 1-7.
25. ORGANIZATION, W. H. 2000. Leishmania/HIV co-infection in south-western Europe 1990-1998: retrospective analysis of 965 cases. World Health Organization.
26. PAUL, J. 2024. Blood and lymphatic infections. *Disease Causing Microbes*. Springer.
27. PIMENTA, P. F., DE FREITAS, V. C., MONTEIRO, C. C., PIRES, A. C. M., SECUNDINO, N. F. C. J. B. S. F. B., TAXONOMY, MEDICAL IMPORTANCE & CONTROL 2018. Biology of the Leishmania– sand fly interaction. 319-339.
28. RAHI, A. 2013. ISSN 2347-954X (Print) Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Iraq: A clinicoepidemiological descriptive study. 1021-1025.
29. RAHI, A. A. 2015. Genetic characterization of Leishmania species causing cutaneous leishmaniasis in Iraq. *Int Res J Eng Technol*, 2, 1057-62.
30. RAJABI, M., MANSOURIAN, A., PILESJö, P., SHIRZADI, M. R., FADAEI, R. & RAMAZANPOUR, J. J. E. M. 2018. A spatially explicit agent-based simulation model of a reservoir host of cutaneous leishmaniasis, *Rhombomys opimus*. 370, 33-49.
31. RASSAM, M., JAWDAT, S., AL-HUSAYIN, N., RIFAAT, L. K. & SUKKER, F. 1985. Biochemical study on Leishmania with some epidemiological applications on leishmaniasis in Iraq. *Journal of biological sciences research (Baghdad)*, 16, 83-103.
32. SLAMA, D., HAOUAS, N., REMADI, L., MEZHOUD, H., BABBA, H. & CHAKER, E. 2014. First detection of Leishmania infantum (Kinetoplastida: Trypanosomatidae) in Culicoides spp. (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae). *Parasit Vectors*, 7, 51.
33. TAVARES, C. A. P., FERNANDES, A. P. & MELO, M. N. 2003. Molecular diagnosis of leishmaniasis. *Expert review of molecular diagnostics*, 3, 657-667.
34. VOLPEDO, G., HUSTON, R. H., HOLCOMB, E. A., PACHECO-FERNANDEZ, T., GANNAVARAM, S., BHATTACHARYA, P., NAKHASI, H. L. & SATOSKAR, A. R. J. E. R. O. V. 2021. From infection to vaccination: reviewing the global burden, history of vaccine development, and recurring challenges in global leishmaniasis protection. 20, 1431-1446.
35. WALKER, D. M., OGHUMU, S., GUPTA, G., MCGWIRE, B. S., DREW, M. E., SATOSKAR, A. R. J. C. & SCIENCES, M. L. 2014. Mechanisms of cellular invasion by intracellular parasites. 71, 1245-1263.